

NATURE AND MEDIA EXPOSURE, AND PARENTS' EMOTIONAL COMPETENCE: IMPLICATIONS ON BEHAVIORAL REGULATION SKILLS OF KINDERGARTNERS WITH SPECIAL NEEDS IN AN INTERVENTION CENTER

Jean Catherine R. Anggam, Miguela B. Napiere, PhD

Graduate School Department, Lourdes College, Cagayan de Oro City, Misamis Oriental, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15588484>

ABSTRACT

In today's rapid, digitally-driven world, children's behavioral and emotional regulation is shaped by their exposure to nature and media, and parental guidance. This study investigated the association between nature and media exposure, and parental emotional competence on the behavioral regulation of kindergartners with special needs in an intervention center. Grounded in Bronfenbrenner's Bio-Ecological Model and Goleman's Emotional Intelligence Theory, the study used a descriptive correlational research design. Data were gathered from eighty (80) randomly selected parents of kindergartners through researcher - made questionnaire, followed by interviews with selected participants to gain deeper insights on the interpretation of the study results. Statistical tools such as descriptive statistics, multiple regression and point-biserial correlation were used to analyze the data. Results revealed that while nature exposure and parents' emotional competence were rated high, they did not significantly correlate with behavioral regulation. Interview results pointed to the importance of consistent therapy and home programs in regulating their children's behavior. In contrast, high level of media exposure, specifically smartphone use, was significantly linked to poor behavioral outcomes. The study recommends the sustenance of the collaborative efforts made by parents and educators to enforce appropriate screen time limits and promote child-friendly digital content. Future researchers are encouraged to explore longitudinal studies and consider other influencing factors such as sleep quality, peer interaction, and parental guidance on children's screen use.

Keywords: *nature exposure, media exposure, behavioral regulation, parental emotional competence*

INTRODUCTION

In today's digital age, young children, including those with special needs, are spending more time using gadgets than playing outdoors. This shift in daily activities has raised concerns among parents, educators, and health professionals. Studies show that while media can sometimes help children learn, too much screen time—especially when unsupervised or involving non-educational content—can negatively affect their ability to control emotions and behavior (Christakis et al., 2019; Muppalla et al., 2023; World Health Organization, 2019).

On the other hand, spending time in nature has been found to help children become calmer, more focused, and more able to control their emotions. Research by Cordiano et al. (2019) supports the idea that outdoor play and interaction with nature promote better self-discipline and emotional well-being. Another important factor is how emotionally aware and responsive parents are. Parents who are good at understanding and handling emotions often create more supportive home environments. These emotionally competent parents help children develop better emotional and behavioral skills (Wang et al., 2024). Goleman (1995) explained that emotional intelligence in adults influences how they guide their children's emotional growth.

The study noticed that while much research has been done on screen time and parenting styles, not many studies look at how media exposure, nature activities, and parents' emotional awareness all work together—especially in children with special needs attending intervention centers. This is the gap the study aimed to fill. The study is especially timely because today's children are growing up surrounded by technology. It is important to understand which factors really help them learn how to manage their emotions and behavior. The researchers of this study wanted to see whether time spent with nature, the amount and type of media used, and how emotionally skilled the parents are, can help children with special needs better control their actions and emotions.

Using Bronfenbrenner's (1979) Bio-Ecological Theory and Goleman's (1995) Emotional Intelligence Theory, this study explored how these different factors—nature, media, and parenting—affect behavioral regulation. The goal was to provide helpful information that schools, parents, and therapists can use to support children's development more effectively.

Research Questions

This study seeks to determine the influence of nature and media exposure, and parents' emotional competence on the behavioral regulation skills of kindergartners with special needs in an intervention center. Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the daily screen time of kindergartners with special needs?
2. What is the kindergartners' extent of media exposure in terms of:
 - 2.1 Type of device; and
 - 2.2 Media content
3. What is the extent of the kindergartners' exposure to nature?
4. What is the parents' level of emotional competence?
5. What is the kindergartners' level of behavioral regulation skills?
6. Do the kindergartners' nature exposure and their parents' emotional competence significantly influence their behavioral regulation skills?
7. Do the kindergartners' behavioral regulation skills significantly differ considering media exposure and daily screen time?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a sequential explanatory mixed-method design, which began with quantitative data collection followed by qualitative inquiry to elaborate on or explain initial findings. This type of mixed methods research that begins with the collection and analysis of quantitative data, followed by qualitative data to help explain or elaborate on the initial findings as described by Toyon (2021). Additionally, the descriptive-correlational design supported analysis of the relationships among variables related to kindergartners' behavioral regulation in an intervention setting. The participants included 80 parents of five-year-old kindergartners diagnosed with special needs enrolled at an intervention center during the 2024–2025 academic year. Participants were selected using simple random sampling from a population of 142 students/parents. Non-parental caregivers such as nannies were excluded to maintain data relevance. All participants voluntarily completed structured questionnaires, which required approximately 15–20 minutes.

The instrument used in the study was a structured survey questionnaire developed based on the concepts from the Nature Relatedness Scale by Nisbet (2009), which measures an individual's affective, cognitive, and experiential relationship with the natural world. The behavioral regulation section was based on the concept of the Emotion Regulation Q-Sort Scale developed by Shields and Cicchetti (1997), which assesses emotion regulation among school-age children and provides insight into behavioral regulation patterns. The parental emotional competence section was based on the Parenting Sense of Competence Scale by Gibaud-Wallston and Wandersman (1978), a validated tool used to assess parents perceived self-efficacy and satisfaction in their parenting role. The section on media consumption was developed by the researcher and grounded in the study's conceptual framework.

The questionnaire used the Likert-scale to guide the participants' responses. Parents were responsible for answering all four sections, providing insights into their child's environmental context and their own emotional competence. Reliability testing through Cronbach's alpha yielded strong internal consistency for the key variables: Nature Exposure ($\alpha = 0.876$), Parental Emotional Competence ($\alpha = 0.829$), and Behavioral Regulation ($\alpha = 0.924$).

RESULTS

Based on the data gathered from this study, the following results are thus presented:

1. The kindergartners in the study spend a significant amount of time on screens each day.
2. The Kindergartners were engaged with digital devices such as smartphones, tablets and televisions for a few hours each day; and the type of content is mostly cartoons and animated videos, followed by educational videos.
3. Nature exposure was rated as generally high, implying that the children had a high level of experience with the outdoors and taken to places such as parks, gardens and other natural spots.
4. The Parents' emotional competence was rated as generally high, implying that they strongly support their children's emotional needs and were highly attuned to recognizing and acknowledging their child's emotions.
5. The Kindergartners' behavioral regulation skills was rated as generally high specifically in completing tasks, showing willingness to share and remaining calm while waiting for attention. However, areas on managing anger, following rules are still in the developing stages, implying that while children displayed great self-regulations in organized activities, their emotional expression and independence in following rules need enhancement.
6. There were no significant relationship found between the association of nature exposure and parents' emotional competence and behavioral regulation skill of the children. However; results of the interview from three (3) parents highlighted the following on the importance of consistent therapy and home programs; and managing behavioral triggers and reinforcements.
7. The type of media devices specifically smartphones were significantly related to the behavioral outcomes of kindergartners. Higher smartphone use was linked to poorer behavioral regulation, possibly due to its overstimulating passive engagement and handy use. On the other hand, tablet use showed a slightly positive correlation, possibly reflecting the use of more educational and interactive content.

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the daily screen time of kindergartners. The data show that most of the children spent their screens daily from 1 – 2 hours (48.75% or 39) and 3 – 4 hours (40% or 32) a day a duration that according to WHO, 2019 consider relatively high for this age group. Additionally, children under the

age of five spend two to three hours a day in front of screens, a significant rise from prior generations which causes behavioral difficulties as stated by Madigan et al., (2019). Excessive screen time, for example, might interfere with important developmental activities, reducing sleep quality, and limit opportunities for social engagement and physical activity. There is a need for educators and parents to encourage screen-free activities that boost social and cognitive development, such as outdoor play, storytelling, and interactive games.

Research Question 1. What is the daily screen time of kindergartners with special needs?

Table 1
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Kindergartners' Daily Screen Time

Range	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 1 hour	5	6.25
1 – 2 hours	39	48.75
3 – 4 hours	32	40.00
More than 4 hours	4	5.00
Total	80	100

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the types of digital devices used by kindergartners. The data identify four primary device categories: television, smartphone, tablet/iPad, and gaming console. Among these, smartphones emerged as the most commonly used device, with 69 out of 80 learners—representing 86.25% of the sample—indicating regular use. This high percentage suggests that smartphones are not only the most accessible digital devices in households but also the most frequently used by young children. Television follows as the second most frequently used device, reported by 55 out of 80 children (68.75%).

Research Question 2. What is the kindergartners' extent of media exposure in terms of;

2.1 Type of Device:

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Devices Used by Kindergartners

Type of Device	Frequency	Percentage
Television	55	68.75
Smartphone	69	86.25
Tablet/iPad	29	36.25

Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of media consumption of the kindergartners. It presents the types of media content most commonly consumed by kindergartners. It has five (5) types of content which are: a) educational videos such as alphabet, numbers and science; b) cartoons and animated shows similarly to Cocomelon, paw patrol or bluey; c) interactive learning apps/games similarly to Roblox or Minecraft; d) YouTube/Online videos; and e) Social Media Content such as TikTok or facebook. The data shows that the type of media content that children engaged or watches with the highest category is the YouTube/ Online Videos which is 72 out of 80 (90%). Guided screen time, along with parental monitoring and content filtering, is important for ensuring that children benefit from technology in age-appropriate and developmentally beneficial ways.

2.2 Media Content

Table 3

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Kindergartners' Media Content Consumption

Type of Media Content	Frequency	Percentage
Educational videos	58	72.5
Cartoons and animated shows	61	76.25
Interactive learning apps/games	14	17.5
YouTube/Online videos	72	90
Social media content	1	1.25

Table 4 presents the frequency, percentage and mean distribution of the kindergartners' exposure to nature as assessed by the parents. The data shows that the majority of kindergartners had a high level of nature exposure, with an overall mean score of 4.04. This finding is indicative that most parents responded that their children enjoyed spending time outdoors, exploring different environments and engaging with natural element. It can further be gleaned from the result that almost 98 percent (97.5% or 78) of parents were highly aware of their children's exposure to nature. This consistency highlights the collective priority put on natural settings throughout the households studied. the findings show that kindergartners have a high amount of nature exposure, as well as an encouraging level of parental awareness and intentionality about the benefits of outdoor spaces.

Research Question 3. What is the extent of the kindergartners' exposure to nature?

Table 4

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Kindergartners' Exposure to Nature Exposure Assessed by the Parents

Score Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51 – 5.00	Very High Extent	1	1.25
3.51 – 4.50	High Extent	78	97.5
2.51 – 3.50	Moderate Extent	1	1.25
1.51 – 2.50	Low Extent	0	0
1.00 – 1.50	Very Low Extent	0	0
Total		80	100.0
Mean			4.04
Interpretation			High Extent
SD			0.24

Table 5 presents the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of parents' emotional competence. The data shows that this was highly evaluated across all parameters, with an overall mean of 4.28 ($SD = 0.23$). This finding is indicative that most parents displayed high levels or 67 of the parents (83.75%) displayed emotional competence. It can further be gleaned that 13 out of 80 parents (16.25%) revealed a very high level of emotional competence. The result exhibited a strong emotional self-awareness of the parents.

The high levels of emotional competence identified among the parents in this study are consistent with emphasizing the importance of parental emotional abilities in children's development. These findings highlight the significance of supporting and improving parental emotional competence as a strategy of promoting beneficial developmental outcomes in children.

Research Question 4. What is the parents' level of emotional competence?

Table 5

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Parents' Emotional Competence

Score Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51 – 5.00	Very High Level	13	16.25
3.51 – 4.50	High Level	67	83.75
2.51 – 3.50	Moderate Level	0	0
1.51 – 2.50	Low Level	0	0
1.00 – 1.50	Very Low Level	0	0
	Total	80	100

Mean	4.28
Interpretation	High Level
SD	0.23

Table 6 shows the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of behavioral regulation of kindergartners. The data show that the level of Kindergartners behavioral regulation was highly aware as assessed by the parents by the overall mean of 3.52 ($SD=0.29$). This finding is indicative that the learners can regulate their behaviors to some extent. It can further be gleaned from the result that almost 52 percent (51.25% or 41) were revealed to have a moderate level of behavioral regulation skills among kindergartners. However, a good number of them (48.75% or 39) were given a high level of behavioral regulation skills among kindergartners. While quantitative data significantly predict the association between nature exposure and parental emotional competence in behavioral regulation, qualitative responses from parent interviews suggests that other practical factor may play a more critical role.

Research Question 5. What is the kindergartners' level of behavioral regulation skills?

Table 6

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Kindergartners' Behavioral Regulation Skills

Score Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51 – 5.00	Very High Level	0	0
3.51 – 4.50	High Level	39	48.75
2.51 – 3.50	Moderate Level	41	51.25
1.51 – 2.50	Low Level	0	0
1.00 – 1.50	Very Low Level	0	0
	Total	80	100
	Mean	3.52	
	Interpretation	High	
	SD	0.29	

Table 7 indicates the multiple regression analysis of nature exposure and parents' emotional competence on the behavioral regulation skills of kindergartners. Since nature exposure and parents' emotional competence were measured using a continuous scale, multiple regression was used, after ensuring that the assumptions of regressions were met. Data revealed no significant relationship between the predictors and the child's behavior regulation skills, $F(2,77)=0.48$, $p=0.62$, $R=0.11$, $R^2=0.01$. In fact, only 1% of the variability of behavior regulation skills can be modestly explained by parents' emotional competence and nature exposure. Several possible findings can be drawn from this result. The low R^2 suggests that kindergartners' behavioral regulation is influenced by environmental, social, and individual factors beyond the two predictors. It is also possible that, while nature exposure and parental emotional competence are beneficial, their effect

on behavioral control is indirect or mediated by other factors, such as parenting methods, child temperament, or the quality of interaction during nature encounters. Similarly, parents who have high emotional competence may not consistently employ those abilities in child-rearing situations due to stress or other limits.

Research Question 6. Do the nature exposure of kindergartners with special needs and their parents’ emotional competence significantly predict their behavior regulation skills?

Table 7
Multiple Regression Analysis of Nature Exposure and Parents’ Emotional Competence on Behavioral Regulation Skills

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
Intercept	4.23	0.74		5.75	<.001
Parents Emotional Competence	-0.11	0.15	-0.163	-0.75	0.46
Nature Exposure	-0.06	0.14	-0.153	-0.38	0.70
Model Summary					
R = 0.11, R ² = 0.01; F = 0.48, df ₁ = 2, df ₂ = 77, p = 0.62					

Table 8 presents the point-biserial correlation between kindergartners’ behavioral regulation skills and various media use variables. Point-biserial correlation was used because the independent variables contain dichotomous data, which are the type of device and type of media content. Data revealed that only the type of device shows significant correlation with behavior regulation skills. Smartphones, in particular, are frequently used unattended and on-the-go, resulting in fragmented engagement and possible overstimulation. A recent study by Radesky et al. (2022) supports this, demonstrating that regular smartphone use among young children is associated with increased irritability and difficulty with emotional regulation, particularly when the device is used to control tantrums or emotional discomfort.

Research Question 7. Do the kindergartners’ behavior regulation skills significantly differ considering media exposure and daily screen time?

Table 8

Point-Biserial Correlation Between Behavioral Regulation Skills and Media Use Variables

Variables	Behavior Regulation Skills	
	r(78)	P
Type of device		
Television	0.04	0.746
Smartphone	-0.34*	0.002
Tablet/iPad	0.26*	0.021
Gaming Console	0.17	0.141
Type of media content		
Educational Videos	0.17	0.125
Cartoons	-0.02	0.876
Interactive Apps/Games	-0.06	0.611
YouTube/Online Videos	0.07	0.528
Social Media Content	-0.07	0.519

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it can be inferred that while kindergartners with special needs are often exposed to supportive environments—such as nature-rich activities and emotionally competent parenting—these factors alone may not directly determine their ability to regulate behavior. This supports the study of Bronfenbrenner’s Ecological Systems Theory (1979) emphasizes the influence of numerous interconnected environments - such as family, media, and natural surroundings on a child's development. Although nature exposure and parental emotional competence were both rated highly, they did not show a statistically significant influence on the children's behavioral regulation skills. This indicate that other factors—possibly including therapy routines, classroom structure, or individual developmental differences—play a more central role in shaping behavioral outcomes.

The most significant outcome came from media exposure. Specifically, the type of gadget used had a bigger influence on children's behavior than screen time itself. Children who often used mobile phones had more difficulties controlling their conduct, probably due to the passive and overstimulating aspect of smartphone activities. The study, furthermore, supports with Domingues-Montanari (2020) that the type of media content children is exposed to can also influence their behavior as to overstimulating activity. In contrast, those who utilized tablets, which are frequently used for more interactive or instructive content, had slightly better behavioral management. This contrast underlines the need of not only limiting screen time, but also being deliberate about the digital experiences that children are exposed to.

While parents reported high levels of emotional awareness and trust in their ability to support their children, as confirmed by Goleman’s (1995) theory that parents with

positive emotional competence tend to influence how they regulate their emotions and connect with their kids. The data did not show a direct correlation with improved behavioral regulation. This emphasizes the complexities of early childhood development and suggests that structured support systems, such as behavioral treatment and consistent household routines, may have a faster effect.

Furthermore, the study's goal of determining whether nature exposure, media use, and parental emotional competence influence the behavioral control of kindergartners with special needs was barely met. Although not all predicted associations were statistically confirmed, the study provided valuable insights. It emphasizes the need of responsible media use and proposes that children gain the most from a combination of environmental support, guided routines, and tailored interventions to help them develop self-regulation abilities.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusions in the study, the researcher presents the following recommendations;

1. Parents may foster children's behavioral development by regulating smartphone usage and encouraging interactive and educational content rather than excessive passive screen time.

2. Teachers may continue to create consistent and clear expectations to help children with special needs develop behavioral regulation skills within a learning environment and engage in regular communication with parents and therapists, in sharing feedbacks and observations to align efforts across home and school setting.

3. Educational Administrators may continue to enhance behavioral regulation activities to implementing interventions that focus on healthy emotional expressions and independent rule-following to strengthen self-regulation skills.

- 4 Policymakers and Child Development Advocates may promote programs that guide responsible digital usage among young children particularly concerning screen time limits and access to quality educational content. Parental education programs focusing on effective behavioral regulation strategies can be expanded within community-based parenting initiatives.

5. Future researchers may explore the long-term effects of digital environments on behavioral regulation through longitudinal research designs. Additional factors such as

sleep patterns, dietary habits, and family dynamics can be examined to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the influences on children's self-regulation skill

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers in this study used a thorough and ethical data gathering method to safeguard the safety of participants and the integrity of the research. Following formal consent from the Intervention Center Director and ethical clearance from the Lourdes College Research Ethics Committee (LCREC), data were gathered utilizing a standardized survey questionnaire. The questionnaire, concentrating on nature exposure, media consumption, parental emotional competence, and behavioural regulation, was presented to parents of kindergartners with special needs.

Informed consent was obtained, and participants were informed of their rights, which included voluntary participation and the option to withdraw at any time. To ensure anonymity, responses were anonymized with unique codes, and no personally identifiable information was gathered. The researchers had exclusive access to the data, which was securely preserved. The study was guided by the Belmont Report's ethical principles of regard for persons, beneficence, and justice, which ensured voluntary participation, participant safety, and fair treatment throughout the research process.

Acknowledgments

First and foremost, the researcher offers praises and heartfelt thanks to God Almighty for His abundant blessings and guidance throughout the research journey, which enabled the successful completion of this study.

The researcher expresses her deep and sincere gratitude to her research adviser, Dr. Miguela B. Napiere, for the opportunity to undertake this research and for her invaluable guidance, support, and mentorship. Dr. Napiere's dedication, vision, and motivation profoundly inspired the researcher. Her instruction in research methodology and her emphasis on clarity in presenting research findings greatly contributed to the development of this work. It has been a great privilege and honor for the researcher to study and work under her guidance.

Acknowledgment is also extended to the professors of the Thesis Writing 1 and Thesis Writing 2 courses. The researcher is especially grateful to Dr. Revina O. Mendoza for her guidance and consistent follow-up during the proposal stage, and to Dr. Ralph Magsalay, who provided expert statistical support that helped refine and streamline the research paper.

Sincere thanks are also extended to the panelists, Dr. Judith C. Chavez, Dr. Alexander F. Suan, Dr. Maria Alona A. Galendez, and Dr. Kriscentti Exzur P. Barcelona for their constructive feedback, insightful suggestions, and encouragement throughout the thesis writing process.

Above all, the researcher takes a moment to recognize the perseverance and resilience demonstrated in overcoming the challenges encountered during the course of

this endeavour, and expresses sincere pride in the accomplishment of this academic milestone.

The researcher extends her deepest thanks to everyone who has been part of this meaningful and transformative journey.

REFERENCES

- Bronfenbrenner, U. (1979). *The ecology of human development: Experiments by nature and design*. Harvard University Press.
- Christakis (2019). How early media exposure may affect cognitive function: A review of results from observations in humans and experiments in mice. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 115, 9851–9858.
- Cordiano (2019). Nature-based education and kindergarten readiness: Nature-based and traditional preschoolers are equally prepared for kindergarten. *The International Journal of Early Childhood Environmental Education*, 6(3), 18.
- Domingues-Montanari (2020). Impact of screen time on children's health and development. *Journal of Pediatrics*.
- Gibaud-Wallston, & Wandersman (1978). Parenting sense of competence scale.
- Goleman, D. (1995). *Working with emotional intelligence*. Bloomsbury
- Madigan (2019). Association Between Screen Time and Children's Performance on a Developmental Screening Test. *JAMA Pediatrics*, 173(3), 244–250.
- Muppalla, S., et al. (2023). Effects of excessive screen time on child development: An updated review and strategies for management. *Cureus*, 15(6), e40608.
- Nisbet (2009). Nature relatedness scale. *Environment and Behavior*, 41, 715–740.
- Radesky (2020). Mobile and interactive media use by young children: The good, the bad, and the unknown. *Pediatrics*, 135(1), 1–3. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2014-2251>.
- Shields (1997). Emotion regulation among school-age children: The development and validation of a new criterion Q-sort scale. *Developmental Psychology*, 33(6), 906–916. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0012-1649.33.6.906>
- Toyon, M. A. (2021). Explanatory sequential design of mixed methods research: Phases and challenges. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 10(5), 253–260. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v10i5.1262>
- Wang, S., (2024). Maternal depression and children's behavioral self-regulation: the role of parenting and children's screen time. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 11(1). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-024-02705-2>
- World Health Organization. (2019). *Guidelines on physical activity, sedentary behavior, and sleep for children under 5 years of age*.

